

1 **Predicting Protein and Pathway Associations for**
2 **Understudied Dark Kinases using Pattern-constrained**
3 **Knowledge Graph Embedding**

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6 Mariah V. Salcedo¹ +, Nathan Gravel²+, Abbas Keshavarzi³, Liang-Chin Huang², Krzysztof J.
7 Kochut*³, Natarajan Kannan*^{1,2}

8
9 ¹ School of Computing, University of Georgia, Athens, Georgia, United States of America

10 ² Institute of Bioinformatics, University of Georgia, Athens, Georgia, United States of America

11 ³ Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, University of Georgia, Athens, Georgia,
12 United States of America

13
14 + these authors contributed equally

15 * Corresponding authors

16
17 Corresponding Author:

18 Natarajan Kannan^{2,3}

19 Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, A318 Life Sciences, University of Georgia,
20 Athens, GA, 30602, United States of America

21
22 Krzysztof J. Kochut¹

23 School of Computing, 415 Boyd GSRC, University of Georgia, Athens, GA, 30602, United
24 States of America

25
26 Email address:

27 nkannan@uga.edu

28 kkochut@uga.edu

29

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31 **Abstract**

32 The 534 protein kinases encoded in the human genome constitute a large druggable class of
33 proteins that include both well-studied and understudied “dark” members. Accurate prediction of
34 dark kinase functions is a major bioinformatics challenge. Here, we employ a graph mining
35 approach that uses the evolutionary and functional context encoded in knowledge graphs (KGs)
36 to predict protein and pathway associations for understudied kinases. We propose a new scalable
37 graph embedding approach, termed RegPattern2Vec, which employs regular pattern constrained
38 random walks to flexibly sample diverse aspects of node context within a KG. RegPattern2Vec
39 learns functional representations of kinases, interacting partners, post-translational modifications,
40 pathways, cellular localization, and chemical interactions from a kinase-centric KG that
41 integrates and conceptualizes data from curated heterogeneous data resources. By
42 contextualizing information relevant for prediction, RegPattern2Vec improves accuracy and
43 efficiency in comparison to other random walk-based graph embedding approaches. We show
44 that the predictions produced by our model overlap with pathway enrichment data produced
45 using experimentally validated Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI) data from both publicly
46 available databases and internal datasets not used in training. Our model also has the advantage
47 of using the collected random walks as biological context in offering some understanding of the
48 obtained predictions. We present three case studies for which we isolated the node sequences
49 associated with a *DarkKinase* node and an associated *Protein-Pathway* prediction. For the dark
50 pseudokinase kinase protein serine kinase H2 (PSKH2), we predict a role in cilium assembly
51 through associations with proteins involved in localizing PSKH2 to the primary cilium
52 membrane. We additionally predict an association for the dark kinase protein kinase cAMP-
53 activated catalytic subunit beta (PRKACB) in diacylglycerol/inositol trisphosphate (DAG/IP3)
54 signaling through interactions with multiple proteins shown to directly affect how the related
55 kinase, Protein Kinase A (PKA), modulates IP3 levels. Finally, we predict a potential role for
56 cyclin dependent kinase 19 (CDK19) in transforming growth factor (TGF)-beta receptor
57 signaling through direct interactions with multiple proteins within the “mediator complex”, a
58 complex shown to promote non-genomic TGF-beta signaling. Overall, the predicted associations
59 between understudied kinases, pseudokinases, and known pathways produced by our model may
60 serve as a conceptual starting point for hypothesis generation and testing.

61 **Introduction**

63 Protein kinases play a fundamental role in cell signaling through the phosphorylation of
64 peptides and proteins on serine, threonine, and tyrosine residues. The 534 protein kinases
65 encoded in the human genome regulate protein activity in diverse pathways including those
66 involved in DNA repair, cell cycle control, and metabolism (Hunter 2009; Johnson et al. 2023;
67 Lahiry et al. 2010; Ochoa et al. 2020). Because dysregulation of protein kinase signaling is
68 causally associated with the pathogenesis of many diseases (Ardito et al. 2017; Oprea et al.
69 2018), much effort has gone into the characterization of their physiological functions (Ayala-
70 Aguilera et al. 2022; Xie et al. 2021) and the development of selective protein kinase inhibitors
71 (Ardito et al. 2017; Attwood et al. 2021; Xie et al. 2021). Despite these efforts, nearly 164 out of
72 the 534 known kinases remain relatively understudied and are referred to as “dark” kinases by
73 the NIH Illuminating the Druggable Genome consortium (IDG) (Berginski et al. 2021; Gillespie

74 et al. 2022; Kelleher et al. 2023). Characterizing the functions of these dark kinases is important
75 because they work in conjunction with other well-studied kinases in signaling pathways and are
76 also frequently mutated, or abnormally expressed, in human diseases such as cancers (Berginski
77 et al. 2021; Brognard & Hunter 2011; Collins et al. 2018; Ravanmehr et al. 2021; Soleymani et
78 al. 2022). While considerable progress has been made in illuminating the functions of several
79 dark kinases, placing these kinases in a pathway or a cell signaling network context remains a
80 major bioinformatics challenge.

81 The compendium of genomic, proteomic and interactome data now available through the
82 efforts of the IDG consortium and numerous investigator-initiated efforts allows for the
83 possibility of inferring the functions and pathways for dark kinases through integrative mining of
84 the known patterns and relationships in existing data. In particular, the development of network-
85 based approaches, such as knowledge graphs (KGs), that relate and link diverse types of protein
86 kinase data in the forms of networks (composed of nodes and edges) enables the prediction of
87 dark kinase functions or pathways through network context (Soleymani et al. 2022). Indeed, KG
88 mining approaches and Machine Learning (ML) methods applied to KGs have been successfully
89 employed in the identification of kinase substrates (Gavali et al. 2022; Nováček et al. 2020),
90 prioritization of understudied kinases (Huang et al. 2018), and identification of disease
91 associations (Bachman et al. 2022; Gyori et al. 2017; Moret et al. 2021; Soleymani et al. 2022).

92 The working premise of these network-based approaches is that proteins (kinases in this
93 case) that share similar network neighbors (such as interacting proteins, downstream substrates,
94 cellular localization, or molecular functions) with well-studied kinases are likely to be involved
95 in common pathways. Several predictive ML methods utilize this premise, however many of
96 these methods are designed for use with homogenous networks (Grover & Leskovec 2016;
97 Perozzi et al. 2014). Homogenous networks have just a single type for nodes and a single type
98 for edges. Whereas heterogenous networks, like KGs, are defined by multiple node and
99 relationship types such as *Drug – targets - Protein* and *Protein – isAssociatedWith –*
100 *DiseaseState*. The use of homogenous networks not only places limitations on the kinds of
101 relationships explored due to limited data and relationship types allowed in the graph, but also
102 limits the already scarce data that can be incorporated into the graph for dark kinases. Other
103 models that can fully leverage heterogenous graphs often suffer from issues of scalability,
104 limiting their predictive power and making the construction of the KG difficult (Alshahrani et al.
105 2021; Bonner et al. 2022; Gavali et al. 2022). Due to these limitations, KGs have not been
106 previously employed to predict pathway associations for dark kinases because dark kinases are
107 sparsely connected in KGs (due to low information content), making it difficult to predict
108 functional associations through local context alone.

109 Random walk-based graph embedding approaches have been proposed to overcome the
110 limitations posed by sparse KGs (Dai et al. 2020). By sampling subsections of the KG, random
111 walk-based methods can scale with larger KGs that would otherwise be too computationally
112 expensive to use in full. While there are many techniques used for data reduction in KGs (Wang
113 et al. 2017), constrained random walks have distinct advantages. Using a constrained “random
114 walk” method on the KG, the graph is stochastically “sampled” such that the multiple data types
115 present within the network can be properly leveraged for predictions. The sampled section of the
116 graph can then be converted into a low dimensional vector representation of the KG such that the
117 biological context relevant for the prediction is accurately captured (Nickel et al. 2015). Utilizing
118 this method has several distinct advantages. First, we can constrain our random walk in such a
119 way that dark kinases and their neighbors are efficiently sampled without overfitting our data.
120 Second the vectorization step in the embedding process converts data into a form in which
121 metrics such as co-occurrence and long-distance connectivity can be calculated (Dong et al.

122 2017). This allows for capturing not only local similarity of the nodes but also more complex and
123 non-trivial associations which lead to novel *Protein-Pathway* predictions for dark kinases in our
124 model.

125 One of the most prominent methods that utilizes random walks is `metpath2vec`.
126 `metpath2vec` preserves the relationships present in the graph during the sampling process by
127 utilizing schemas (ordered set of specific node or edge types). By specifying what node/edge
128 types should be sampled, integration of different data types can be fully leveraged for
129 predictions, thus accurately capturing structure of heterogeneous graphs. However, creating such
130 meta-paths for complex heterogeneous KGs, often with no well-defined schema, is challenging
131 and time consuming with the performance of the model being highly dependent on the chosen
132 meta-path (series of nodes). A number of previous attempts to automatically generate meta-paths
133 have been reported in the literature (Meng et al. 2015; Wan et al. 2020; Yang et al. 2018) but
134 they all rely on fixed-length meta-paths, which prevents accurate representation of latent and
135 hierarchical structure encoded in large KGs.

136 Here we employ `RegPattern2Vec` (Keshavarzi et al. 2021), a novel approach for learning
137 on semantic data to predict new pathway associations for dark kinases. `RegPattern2Vec` directly
138 addresses limitations of previous models and provides more accurate predictions by precisely
139 capturing relevant node/edge context in a scalable manner using regular patterns. Unlike
140 `metpath2vec`, `RegPattern2Vec` can make node-association predictions without the need to
141 specify the entirety of the schema. This allows us to meaningfully sample the KG without the
142 need for specifying multiple meta-paths. Our group has previously demonstrated the utility of
143 `RegPattern2Vec` in link prediction tasks (Keshavarzi et al. 2021). Here we have improved upon
144 our previous algorithm to allow for more representative sampling of neighbor nodes for
145 biological KG embedding and ML applications.

146 Overall, we were able to successfully employ `RegPattern2Vec` to capture the node/edge
147 context more accurately within our KG. After sampling, the ML technique (link prediction) is
148 employed to predict new associations between dark kinases and characterized pathways. We
149 place 34 dark kinases for which we have consistent, high confidence predictions produced
150 through replicate runs (with differing hyperparameters) in a pathway context and based on an
151 analysis of the meta-paths navigated for three selected dark kinases, we provide biological
152 interpretations of the predicted pathway associations.

153 The `RegPattern2Vec` pipeline is available at the GitHub repository
154 (<https://github.com/gravelCompBio/RegPattern2Vec>).

155

156 **Materials & Methods**

157 **2.1: Knowledge Graph Architecture.**

158 KGs are very similar to Heterogeneous Information Networks. An Information Network
159 is a directed graph $G = (V, E)$, composed of vertices (also called nodes) and edges, with an
160 associated node type mapping function $\phi: V \rightarrow A$ and an edge type mapping function $\psi: E \rightarrow R$
161 (Shi et al. 2016). Each node $v \in V$ belongs to one particular node type in the node type set
162 $A: \phi(v) \in A$, and each edge $e \in E$ belongs to a particular edge type in the edge type set
163 $R: \psi(e) \in R$. An Information Network is called a Heterogeneous Information Network if the sets
164 A and R both contain more than one element, that is, there are multiple labels (types) for graph
165 nodes and multiple labels (types) for edges. If sets A and R are singletons, the Information
166 Network is called a Homogeneous Information Network (all nodes in the network are of the
167 same type and all edges are of the same type). While Heterogeneous Information Networks
168 require that if two edges belong to the same edge type, the two edges share the same starting

169 node type as well as the same ending node type, KGs do not. That is, the same edge (relation)
170 type can be applied to different starting node types and different ending node types. This is also
171 the case in the Resource Description Framework (RDF) (Cyganiak et al. 2014; W3C 2014), a
172 notation often used to represent KGs. RDF is based on the notion of triples of the form *Subject-*
173 *predicate-Object* (Cyganiak et al. 2014) representing edges connecting nodes in the graph.

174 For example, in a KG representing information about protein kinases, a node (entity)
175 representing a protein dark kinase *CDK13* (cyclin dependent kinase 13) can be connected by an
176 edge (relationship) labeled *hasPathway* to a node representing a pathway
177 *NeutrophilDegranulation*, which represents the knowledge that *CDK13* participates in the
178 pathway *NeutrophilDegranulation*. In such a KG, *CDK13* may be connected to other nodes
179 using different labels (*hasPathway*), such as, *CDK13 – hasMolelcularFunction—CyclinBinding*,
180 *CDK13 – hasBiologicalProcess—GranulocyteActivation* and *CDK13 – hasCellularComponent—*
181 *GolgiApparatus*. Other protein kinases can additionally be included in the neighborhood context,
182 through shared nodes, such as the shared molecular function of *CyclinBinding* between dark
183 kinase *CDK13* and light kinase *CDK6* (cyclin dependent kinase 6). Here, edges have multiple
184 labels and destination nodes are of different types, which indicates that it is a heterogeneous KG.

185 Given a Heterogeneous Information Network $G = (V, E)$ (as defined above), the
186 network's schema is a directed graph, $S = (A, R)$, based on G 's node type mapping $\phi: V \rightarrow A$
187 and its edge (relation) type mapping $\psi: E \rightarrow R$. S is a directed graph defined over node types A ,
188 with edges as relations from R . Similarly, the schema of a KG represented in RDF is represented
189 in RDFS (RDF Schema (W3C 2014)). For example, given the *CDK13* examples above, the
190 schema would contain the edges *Protein – participatesIn – Pathway*, *Protein – isClassifiedAs—*
191 *KinaseFamily*, and *Protein – isLocatedIn – CellularLocation*. The schema, sometimes referred
192 to as a meta-knowledge graph, or meta-graph, specifies constraints on the use of the edge labels
193 to certain types of starting and ending nodes (subjects and objects in RDF). Also, given a KG
194 schema, we can create a KG conforming to the schema containing many individuals (nodes).

195

196 **2.2: Data Sources and Curation of Datasets for Knowledge Graph Generation.**

197 To construct our human kinase-centric KG, we gathered data from multiple publicly
198 available curated resources (Fig. 1A). Nodes and edges within the graph were further integrated
199 under more general node and relationship labels (also referred to as node types and edge types
200 respectively) such as *Disease* (Fig. 1A and Fig. 2C). We further filtered the information included
201 within our KG to avoid redundancy (described below). Figure 1B shows basic statistics of
202 different edges and their source and target nodes. The final KG contained 1,064,097 nodes of 11
203 types and 6,279,374 associations of 13 types.

204 The node types *Protein* and *FunctionalDomain* were populated with information on
205 human kinase classification, functional domains, structure, and Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI)
206 data extracted from the following databases: ProKinO (McSkimming et al. 2015), Dark Kinase
207 Knowledgebase (darkkinome.org) (Berginski et al. 2021), UniProt (UniProt 2021), PDBe-KB
208 (Velankar et al. 2010), Pfam v33.1 (Mistry et al. 2021), and STRING v11 (Szklarczyk et al.
209 2019). Protein Post-Translational Modifications (PTMs) associations were also included within
210 our KG under node type *PTM* and were retrieved from iPTMnet v5 (Ross et al. 2017). The
211 *Chemical* and *Disease* node types were populated from the Comparative Toxicogenomics
212 Database (Davis et al. 2021) (protein-chemical, protein-disease, chemical-disease, and chemical-
213 GO term associations) as well as cancer mutation data from the Catalogue of Somatic Mutations

214 in Cancer (COSMIC) (Tate et al. 2019). The Genomics of Drug Sensitivity in Cancer (GDSC)
215 (Yang et al. 2013) database was used for drug activity data. The *Chemical* node type additionally
216 include information on kinase associated and ligand interaction motifs and ligand activity
217 retrieved from Kinase-Ligand Interaction Fingerprints and Structures (KLIFS) (Kanev et al.
218 2021) and Pharos (Sheils et al. 2021), respectively. Gene ontology terms and pathway
219 information regarding human kinases were retrieved from the Gene Ontology v2019_11 (Gene
220 Ontology 2021) (*GOTerm* node type) and Reactome v76 (Jassal et al. 2020) (*Pathway* node
221 type), respectively.

222

223 **2.3: Further Filtering of Data Sources to Reduce Redundancy.**

224 The retrieved datasets were further curated prior to KG generation and population. All
225 *Protein-Pathway* associations obtained from Reactome were split into manually curated
226 associations (evidence=TAS) and predicted associations (evidence=IEA), only manually curated
227 associations were included in our KG. Additionally, due to the hierarchical nature of the data
228 taken from Reactome (i.e., *Pathways* are often organized into parent-child relationships), we
229 eliminated high level pathways as they were deemed too general for our experiments. For
230 example, we filtered out the pathways beneath “Disease” (R-HSA-1643685) but not beneath
231 “Infectious disease” (R-HSA-5663205). This was done not only to reduce redundancy in the data
232 but also to ensure the vector embeddings created from our KG, for link prediction, were not
233 overfitted to highly connected nodes (often referred to as *hubs*). Similar filtering was done with
234 Protein-GO term associations retrieved from Gene Ontology- GO terms with more than 5000
235 associations were removed. Additionally, Protein-GO terms were given separate node and edge
236 types in the KG according to the *MolecularFunction*, *CellularComponent*, and *BiologicalProcess*
237 terms.

238 Additional filtering to increase confidence in the data within our KG was performed
239 using various strategies specific to the data source. Only PPIs (STRING) directly involving a
240 kinase and with an experimental data score of more than 700 were included in our KG and only
241 PTMs (iPTMnet) with a confidence score of more than 1.0 were included in the graph.
242 Additionally, Pfam entries with the protein kinase domains (“Pkinase” and “Pkinase_Tyr”) were
243 removed.

244

245 **2.4: Creation of Curated Kinase Knowledge Graph for Kinase-Pathway Link Prediction.**

246 The KG used in our link prediction experiments described here contains several node
247 types such as *Protein*, GO Terms (*BiologicalProcess*, *MolecularFunction*, and
248 *CellularComponent*), *Disease*, and other types. The schema organization is shown in Fig. 2B.
249 The dotted line represents the path taken for the specified schema [*Protein*, any node not *Protein*
250 and not *Pathway*, *Protein*, *Pathway*] for the final edge *Protein* —*participatesIn* — *Pathway*,
251 which represents the known (existing) edges, retrieved from Reactome (Jassal et al. 2020)
252 included in our knowledge graph, and unknown (previously not reported) links that we are
253 predicting. In addition, the *Protein* type includes the understudied kinases (referred to as
254 *DarkKinases*), well-studied kinases (referred to as *LightKinases*), and other human proteins. This
255 distinction is important, as it gives us the ability to make predictions for a subset of proteins. The

256 edge types (edges in the schema) are not labeled here, as we do not consider them in our method
257 described here. Instead, we only rely on the types of source and target nodes. The loop edge
258 going back to the *Protein* type indicates the *Protein-Protein* Interaction relation, which is
259 included in our knowledge graph.

260

261 **2.5: Link Prediction Workflow.**

262 In the experiments and results presented in this paper, we used our novel node embedding
263 approach, called RegPattern2Vec. It is used as the first step in our link prediction process to
264 produce vector representations for the nodes in the graph and formulate the link prediction as a
265 classification problem. A ML model was trained using the combined vectors of existing pairs of
266 nodes connected by an edge (link) of interest. The outline of the method is illustrated in Fig. 2A.
267 We discuss each step of our link prediction method in the subsequent sections.

268

269 **2.6: Regular Pattern Selection and its Usage in Random Walks.**

270 Given a Heterogenous Information Network (as defined above), we have used regular
271 patterns of the form $H[^T]^+ HT$ for link prediction tasks, i.e., edges (links) between nodes of
272 type H and T . In the pattern, H is a source node type and T is a target node type of the link of
273 interest, respectively. Additionally, $[^T]$ denotes any node type different than T (in regular
274 expressions terminology it is known as the complement operator), and $[^T]^+$ denotes a repetition
275 (sequence) of one or more node types that are different than T . The overall pattern requires that
276 any random walk must match the specified sequence of node types, in that a walk must begin
277 with a node of type H , then it must be followed by one or more nodes of type different than T ,
278 then a node of type H , which must then be immediately followed by a node of type T . That last
279 step in the walk is the link (edge) being predicted.

280 Simply put, the regular pattern is defined as a schema subgraph that should include only
281 the node types that are relevant for a specific problem. An example regular pattern subgraph is
282 shown in Fig. 2B. Unlike in the metapath2vec method (Dong et al. 2017), the schema graph
283 pattern represents multiple paths (walks) that can be used to predict missing links. Here, we aim
284 to predict *Protein-Pathway* links and the random walks of interest are constrained by a regular
285 pattern that connects node types and edge types most relevant to the links being predicted. Here,
286 when generating *Protein-Pathway* predictions we have defined the regular pattern as *Protein*
287 $[^Pathway]^+ Protein Pathway$ and each random walk instance must match it. Each walk starts
288 from a *Protein* node. Selecting the next nodes on a walk is based on the existing graph nodes and
289 matching the neighbor's type in the regular pattern. When a random walk reaches a *Pathway*
290 node, it follows the pattern in reverse order and does so until a certain number of steps (nodes) in
291 the walk are reached, or when it reaches a termination node, i.e., when there is no neighbor to
292 match the pattern.

293

294 **2.7: Capturing Semantic Relationships between Proteins and Pathways in Deep Learning.**

295 RegPattern2Vec uses a modified skip-gram model presented in (Dong et al. 2017) to
296 generate vector representations for the nodes of the KG. The random walks generate sequences
297 of nodes, which resemble natural language sentences. The ML model simultaneously captures

298 the local structure of the graph and types of the nodes and encodes them as vector
299 representations. Figure 3 shows learned vector representation of nodes in the vector space using
300 Principal Component Analysis (PCA), a standard dimensionality reduction technique. For the
301 *Protein-Pathway* predictions, we just consider the nodes to be of three types: “*Protein*”,
302 “*Pathway*”, and “*Others*” when learning representation for the nodes. The separation of nodes in
303 PCA shows the node types and their network context is captured by our vector representation.

304

305 **2.8: Biased Random Walk Constrained by a Regular Pattern.**

306 As this work considered undirected graphs, enumerating all the paths of a given graph is
307 computationally infeasible. The solution is to sample a subset of paths from all possible paths
308 from a random distribution. The random walk constrained by a regular pattern is selected to
309 generate walks of arbitrary length, which is controlled by “*walk length*” hyperparameter. Having
310 the undirected heterogeneous network and a selected regular pattern, the random walk can be
311 started from each instance of a starting node type in the pattern. As we want all the nodes to
312 possibly appear in our walks, iterating over all of them would be desirable. It is obvious that if
313 we repeat the walk from each node (not all KG nodes may begin a walk, as constrained by the
314 regular pattern), we will discover more walks as the node might link to multiple nodes of the
315 same type. We call this hyperparameter “*number of walks*” (referred to as NW in Results
316 sections 3.2-3.3). We will discuss how to choose the hyperparameter and the analysis of their
317 impact in the Results section 3.2-3.3. The next step for each node is to select a node from the
318 adjacent nodes based on the established regular pattern. This might result in multiple choices,
319 and this is where the randomization comes to play. RegPattern2Vec can utilize random
320 distribution created by a user-defined function to generate the same probability for all the nodes
321 or use an arbitrary distribution. To implement the random walk collection process, a regular
322 pattern is converted to a Deterministic Finite Automaton (DFA), denoted by M , and each of the
323 possible walk steps is mapped to the DFA. The DFA M is used to check if transitions are
324 allowed (an edge between two nodes); hence, a disallowed transition gets a zero probability and
325 is not used in the random walks.

326 On the other hand, in scale-free networks where the degree distribution follows the power
327 law, some nodes may have a high degree of incoming/outgoing edges (known as *hubs*). Because
328 such high degree nodes can dominate random walks and, consequently, representation learning,
329 one popular way to address this issue is to bias the walks by inverse of degrees of nodes (Grover
330 & Leskovec 2016), where the probability of choosing a node v^{i+1} from v^i is calculated by
331 normalizing the inverse of degrees of all neighbors of v^i . Although this approach lowers the
332 probability of selecting high degree nodes, it biases the random walk toward low-degree nodes.
333 To accomplish a better distribution and avoid both biases, we proposed the next node selection
334 formula below:

$$P(v^{i+1}|v^i, M) = \begin{cases} g(r^i) \frac{\frac{1}{|N_{v^{i+1}}|}}{\sum_{v \in N_{v^i}} \frac{1}{|N_v|}} & (v^i, r^i, v^{i+1}) \text{ is an edge in the graph and the} \\ & \text{transition from } v \text{ to } v \text{ is allowed in } M \\ 0 & (v^i, r^i, v^{i+1}) \text{ is an edge, but the transition is undefined} \\ 0 & (v^i, r^i, v^{i+1}) \text{ does not exist in the graph} \end{cases}$$

336

337 In the formula, v^i denotes the current node and the candidate node for next step is $v^{i+1} \in$
338 N_{v^i} . $|N_v|$ denotes the degree of node v , and N_{v^i} is the set of all the neighbors of node v^i . $g(r^i)$
339 is the proportion of the edges of type r^i among all edges of node v^i . . Therefore, we first
340 randomly choose one edge (relation) type and then use the probability distribution by the inverse
341 of node degrees to select the next node in the walk, but only among the nodes connected by the
342 selected edge type.

343

344 2.9: Link Prediction as a Classification Problem.

345 For each pair of *Protein-Pathway* associations, we combined their vector embeddings
346 utilizing a widely used Hadamard product (Grover & Leskovec 2016; Lin et al. 2015; Minervini
347 et al. 2015). The resulting vector is used as features to train a Logistic Regression model.
348 Training the model additionally requires generating negative examples for *Protein-Pathway*
349 association pairs which is difficult as resources with true biological negatives, such as Negatome
350 (Blohm et al. 2014), do not exist for our *Pathway* data type. To generate negative examples, we
351 must first work under the closed-world assumption. This assumes that all information needed is
352 provided, so for a statement to be true it must be explicitly stated to be so, thus a lack of a
353 statement denotes that it is false (this contrasts with the open-world assumption in which
354 statements can be true without them being explicitly known to be so). For our relation of interest
355 (predicted link), we randomly select a head and tail node that are not connected by an edge in the
356 graph. The embeddings of such nodes are then combined to produce negative examples. This
357 process is repeated until the number of negative examples matches the positive examples.

358

359 Results

360 In this work, we propose a new guided random walk approach for KGs, known as
361 RegPattern2Vec, used for the prediction of pathway associations for dark kinases. To generate
362 *Protein-Pathway* predictions, we first constructed a protein kinase KG by integrating curated
363 data from various resources populating the graph with nodes on molecular function, disease
364 association, protein-protein associations and more (see Materials & Methods section 2.2). The
365 resulting KG consisted of 1,064,097 nodes (entities) and 6,279,373 edges (relationships) (Table
366 S1, Fig. 1B). RegPattern2Vec was then used to sample the large KG into sequences of nodes.

367 Sampling was guided by regular patterns from RegPattern2Vec. Using such patterns, we
368 generate several walk paths (or a list of sequential nodes in the network) that are used for
369 representation learning. This allows the sampling to capture different sub-structures in the graph
370 (covering different meta-paths) without explicitly designing walks for them.

371 After sampling, the model then learned vector embeddings for each node in the collected
372 paths, utilizing a Natural Language Processing (NLP) model similar to metapath2vec (Dong et
373 al. 2017). Link predictions utilizing the embeddings were then formulated as binary classification
374 tasks and predictions were made for *Protein-Pathway* associations using a Logistic Regression
375 model. For more details, refer to the Materials & Methods section 2.9.

377 **3.1: Benchmarking RegPattern2Vec's Predictive Performance with metapath2vec and** 378 **Demonstrating Improved Accuracy.**

379 To evaluate the accuracy of our method and note any improvements from metapath2vec,
380 a test set was first generated by excluding 50% of the known *Protein-Pathway* associations from
381 the training set. The training examples were generated using the process detailed in the Materials
382 & Methods (section 2.5-2.9). To compare our method to metapath2vec, we produced AUC ROC
383 curves for both models. Multiple curves were generated for the metapath2vec model as multiple
384 meta-paths were used resulting in variability in the model's performance (Fig. 4). Metapath 1
385 ('*Protein*', '*FunctionalDomain*', '*Protein*', '*Pathway*', '*Protein*') showed the best performance,
386 based on 10-fold cross-validation, with an f1-score of 0.87 and AUC ROC of 0.94 for *Protein-*
387 *Pathway* prediction. In contrast, RegPattern2Vec, achieved an f1-score of 0.90 and AUC ROC of
388 0.96 on the same training and testing datasets (Fig. 4).

389 Overall, we show that unlike metapath2vec, RegPattern2Vec does not need predefined
390 precise meta-paths for capturing contextual information in KGs. Despite working in a similar
391 manner, RegPattern2Vec achieved higher performance than metapath2vec with the predefined
392 meta-paths provided.

394 **3.2: Investigating the Impact of Hyperparameters on RegPattern2Vec's Predictive** 395 **Variability Among Replicate Runs.**

396 Due to the nature of the random walks, there is an intrinsic level of variability with the
397 predictions made by our model. Although the exact same sequence of nodes will not be sampled
398 each time, there should be a larger context within the embedding space that identifies patterns
399 useful for predictions for the dark kinases sampled. Therefore, overlaps in the *Pathway-Protein*
400 predictions made by our model using different hyperparameters are expected. To demonstrate
401 our model's robustness, we measure the predictive consistency while modifying hyperparameters
402 across three replicates (runs that all have the same hyperparameters) and compared these results.
403 The percentage of *Protein-Pathway* predictions that overlap (within all replicates) was used as a
404 metric for our model's robustness. This analysis also revealed the variability in the overlap of the
405 *Protein-Pathway* predictions on a per kinase basis (for both light and dark kinases). This
406 variability may be due to imbalances in the data available for each kinase. Of note, greater
407 variability was seen amongst dark kinases, with the highest overlap being 29 and the lowest
408 overlap being 0 (for the hyperparameter 40 NW with 95% confidence cutoff).

409 One source of variability within our model is directly controlled by the hyperparameter
410 “*number of walks* (NW)”, which specifies the number of times a node should be sampled as the
411 starting node during the random walk process (refer to Materials & Methods section 2.8).
412 Repeating the walk from a specified node allows for more complete characterization of neighbor
413 nodes, often allowing for more node/edge types to be captured and considered in downstream
414 analysis which is especially important when working with sparse data.

415 To find the optimal NW, the same starting node was used for generating paths in the
416 random walk anywhere from 10 to 80 times. This process was repeated, resulting in a total of
417 three replicates for each variation of the NW hyperparameter. Overlap between the *Protein-
418 Pathway* predictions obtained through replicate hyperparameter conditions were then compared.
419 From this analysis, we sought to identify the smallest value for the hyperparameter NW that can
420 accurately capture local structure and node context within the graph to make consistent
421 predictions (as determined by replicate overlap). This analysis revealed that changing the
422 hyperparameter NW did not drastically change the number of overlapping *Protein-Pathway*
423 predictions between replicate datasets (Fig. S1). Of note the value of 40 for the hyperparameter
424 NW (abbreviated 40 NW) generated the most consistent predictions among the NW parameters
425 tested, with a mean of ~22% overlapping pathways across three 0.7 cutoff replicates when
426 averaging overlap over all kinases even when utilizing a range of confidence cutoffs from 0.7-
427 0.95 (Fig. S1). As a result of this benchmark, we determined that 40 NW is the optimal
428 hyperparameter for predicting *Protein-Pathway* relationships in the current KG, as it performs
429 slightly better (as measured by replicate overlap) than the more computationally intensive
430 hyperparameter values tested.

431 432 **3.3: Hyperparameter Optimization Results in Consistent Replicate Pathway Predictions for** 433 **23 Dark Kinases across Different Replicate Runs.**

434 After finding the optimal value for the hyperparameter NW (Fig. S1), we decided to
435 investigate the overlap of all *Protein-Pathway* predictions produced by our previous analysis in
436 which we test the hyperparameter NW (from 10-80 with a total of three replicate runs for each
437 condition). The overlapping predictions present amongst highly variable walks would suggest
438 that these predictions are made based on nodes more often sampled within our network. After
439 filtering for predictions that have over 0.95 confidence, only 95 dark kinase *Protein-Pathway*
440 predictions emerged that were present in all replicates of all variations of NW tested (a total of
441 24 datasets) (Fig. 5A), resulting in representative *Protein-Pathway* predictions for 34 of the
442 unique dark kinases in our dataset (Table S2). The top ten kinases (ranked according to number
443 of predictions that overlap) are shown in Fig. 5B. Of note, many of the *Protein-Pathway*
444 predictions generated by our model were highly consistent (either in pathways with similar
445 function or protein family involvement) on a per kinases basis (Table S2). For example, for the
446 dark kinase VRK serine/threonine kinase 3 (VRK3), seven out of ten predictions were related to
447 Toll Like Receptor (TLR) cascades, and five out of five *Protein-Pathway* predictions for the
448 dark kinase protein kinase, membrane associated tyrosine/threonine 1 (PKMYT1) were related to
449 cell cycle control (Table S2). We further focused on a subset of dark kinases for path analysis
450 described below.

451

452 **3.4: Path Analysis Provides Context for Prediction Associations Between Understudied** 453 **PRKACB and DAG/IP3 Signaling.**

454 The dark kinase protein kinase cAMP-activated catalytic subunit beta (PRKACB) was
455 amongst the kinases identified with the highest overlap of *Protein-Pathway* predictions (Fig.
456 5B). Related to the well-studied kinase Protein Kinase A (PKA) recently shown to have a role in
457 regulating levels of the known inducer for calcium signaling inositol trisphosphate (IP3)
458 (Barodia et al. 2022; Kania et al. 2017; Ould Amer & Hebert-Chatelain 2018), PRKACB appears
459 to be similarly involved in calcium regulation and modulation (Palencia-Campos et al. 2020).
460 Eight out of the ten pathways identified were directly linked to calcium regulation (Table S2). To
461 contextualize the predictions made by our model for PRKACB, we created a subgraph displaying
462 common nodes traversed during the random walk process for the node representing the
463 Reactome *Protein-Pathway* prediction R-HSA-1489509 (*DAG/IP3Signaling*). A portion of the
464 subgraph highlighting the common nodes sampled between different paths are shown in Fig. 5C.
465 The nodes found in all sampled paths are more likely to represent nodes which are important for
466 providing the context that results in the shared *Protein-Pathway* prediction. The entirety of the
467 subgraph (Data S1) displays all nodes with the addition of unconnected nodes that only appear in
468 one path generated during the random walk process.

469 The highly sampled nodes of the subgraph shown in Fig. 5C, reveal that *PRKACG*
470 (protein kinase cAMP-activated catalytic subunit gamma), *PRKAR2A* (protein kinase cAMP-
471 dependent type II regulatory subunit alpha) (Manchev et al. 2014; Wei et al. 2021) and
472 (calcium/calmodulin dependent protein kinase kinase 2) *CAMKK2* (Najar et al. 2021) are nodes
473 often sampled for the *DAG/IP3Signaling* prediction. The nodes being sampled multiple times
474 demonstrate our model's ability to leverage PPIs to infer pathway involvement. Additional nodes
475 of interest that are often sampled for this prediction include PPIs between PRKACB (protein of
476 interest) and both A-kinase anchor protein 28 (AKA28), and cGMP-specific 3',5'-cyclic
477 phosphodiesterase (PDE5A). Both proteins are shown to have biologically relevant functions that
478 support the *Protein-Pathway* prediction for PRKACB's involvement with DAG/IP3 signaling.
479 AKA28 has been shown to bind to type II regulatory subunits of PKA (related to our dark
480 kinase) and anchors/targets PKA to discrete locations within the cell (Kennedy & Scott 2015;
481 Kultgen et al. 2002; Omar & Scott 2020; Sarma et al. 2010). PDE5A is a phosphodiesterase that
482 regulates intracellular levels of cAMP and AMP (Peng et al. 2020). Together, these observations
483 support the predicted link/association between understudied PRKCB kinase and DAG/IP3
484 signaling pathway.

485

486 **3.5: Predicted Association of Understudied CDK19 in TGF-beta Receptor Signaling:** 487 **Interpretability with Path Analysis and Validation with PPI Datasets.**

488 To further explore the biological relevance of our predictions for dark kinases, we
489 compared our *Protein-Pathway* predictions to Reactome datasets generated using Protein
490 Interaction and Proximity (PPI) data for dark kinases not included in our training data. PPI data
491 was obtained from the Dark Kinase Knowledgebase (Berginski et al. 2021). Of note, many
492 kinases in this dataset did not have sufficient protein-interactors to perform Reactome pathway

493 enrichment analysis. For the 50 dark kinases with a sufficient number of identified interactors,
494 the overlap between the *Protein-Pathway* predictions generated by our link prediction and the
495 Reactome enrichment generated by PPI data were compared. Figure 6A shows the top ten dark
496 kinases ranked according to *Protein-Pathway* prediction overlap abundance and Table S3
497 provides the pathway information for all dark kinases with overlap seen. Among the dark kinases
498 with the highest overlap from this comparison was cyclin dependent kinase 19 (CDK19), a dark
499 kinase belonging to the cyclin-dependent kinase superfamily (Malumbres 2014).

500 After performing similar subgraph analysis to that previously described for PRKACB
501 (Results section 3.4), we were able to isolate nodes commonly traversed for the protein node of
502 interest (*CDK19*) and the pathway node of interest *TGF-betaReceptorSignaling* (R-HSA-
503 170834) (Fig. 6B). Again, only a subset of the paths are shown for ease of viewing. The entirety
504 of the subgraph (Data S2) displays all nodes with the addition of unconnected nodes that only
505 appear in one path generated during the random walk process. For the dark protein kinase
506 CDK19 with the link prediction of TGF-beta receptor signaling, two “key” nodes hubs were
507 identified including *CCNC* (cyclin-c) and *CDK8* (cyclin dependent kinase 8). Recent total
508 mRNA sequencing has demonstrated that loss of *CCNC* could activate the transforming growth
509 factor (TGF)-beta signaling pathway (Tang et al. 2021). *CDK8* has also been implicated in TGF-
510 beta signaling through previous studies showing they drive Smad transcriptional action and
511 turnover in TGF-beta pathways (Alarcón et al. 2009). Through interactions with several
512 members of the mediator of RNA polymerase II transcription (*MED*) protein family, *CDK19* can
513 also indirectly exploit the relationship between *CDK8* and TGF-beta receptor signaling. It
514 appears that both *CDK19*, and *CDK8* have been shown to directly interact with not just each
515 other but *MED12*, as well as *CCNC*, forming a complex collectively termed the “Mediator
516 Complex” (Fant & Taatjes 2019). This complex interacts with DNA-bound transcription factors
517 and with RNA polymerase II (*Pol II*) to both activate and repress gene expression, with mediator
518 subunit *MED12* promoting TGF-beta signaling through both canonical regulation of
519 transcription and non-genomic activity (Weber & Garabedian 2018). Taken together this
520 suggests that while direct connections contribute to the predictive power of the model the
521 surrounding node context can also reinforce these connections and can heavily contribute to
522 predictions made.

523

524 **3.6: Predicted Association Between Understudied PSKH2 and Cilium Assembly.**

525 *Protein-Pathway* predictions produced by our model were additionally validated against
526 data produced internally using mass-spectrometry based proteomics to find protein binding
527 partners (Byrne et al. 2022). Despite the lack of published information, our model was still able
528 to produce *Protein-Pathway* predictions for the understudied kinase protein serine kinase H2
529 (*PSKH2*). The understudied kinase *PSKH2*, is a pseudokinase (Byrne et al. 2022) and paralog of
530 the Golgi-associated canonical dark kinase protein serine kinase H1 (*PSKH1*)(Brede et al. 2000).
531 Currently, the Dark Kinase Knowledgebase (Berginski et al. 2021) lists only ten known protein
532 interactors for *PSKH2* and with so few identified interactors Reactome enrichment could not be
533 performed using this dataset. We utilized, an independent mass-spectrometry based analysis of
534 *PSKH2* interacting partners which identified ~174 binding proteins (Byrne et al. 2022) that (at

535 the time of our analysis) were not included in any databases used in training, for the Reactome
536 enrichment.

537 Comparing the overlap in *Protein-Pathway* predictions (40 NW dataset) with the data
538 generated using mass-spectrometry as an input for Reactome enrichment, 18 pathways were
539 shown to overlap (Table S4). The previously characterized subgraph visualization (Results
540 section 3.4) was then performed, with five random paths chosen for visualization of the nodes
541 commonly traversed for the protein node of interest (*PSKH2*) and the prediction node of interest
542 (*CiliumAssembly* R-HSA- 5617833) (Fig. 7 and Data S3). Through this analysis one major “key”
543 node hub was identified, *UNC119B*. unc-119 lipid binding chaperone B (UNC119B), is a protein
544 that plays a key role in the localization of ciliary proteins by binding to N-myristoylated proteins
545 and masking the hydrophobic lipid from hydrophilic cytosol, therefore facilitating trafficking to
546 the primary cilium or the immunological synapse (Stroukov et al. 2019; Yelland et al. 2021).
547 Many of the additional commonly traversed nodes belong to larger families of proteins known to
548 play important roles in cilium assembly such as tubulins and dyneins. Thus, further
549 characterization of these proteins can shed light on the role of PSKH2 in cilium assembly.

550 Overall, through our analysis of the paths utilized by the model as context for the link
551 prediction process, we demonstrated that our modified random walk approach, RegPattern2Vec,
552 can successfully sample multiple types of nodes and edges. These findings support our notion
553 that our model preserves both local and latent structure through appropriate neighbor sampling
554 and therefore provides the node context needed to make predictions. The predictions made by
555 our model regarding dark kinases allow us to explore dark kinases of interest in a pathway
556 context, giving us an idea of how these kinases may function and relate to other proteins.

557

558 Discussion

559 In this work we present a new network approach to predict pathway associations for
560 understudied dark kinases by leveraging network context of well-studied kinases. We predict
561 pathway associations for dark kinases and propose a new graph embedding approach,
562 RegPattern2Vec, which has significant advantages over the previously proposed metapath2vec
563 approach for KG embedding. First, unlike metapath2vec, RegPattern2Vec does not require pre-
564 defined knowledge of KG schema to define the paths. Second, because RegPattern2Vec does not
565 use fixed length meta-paths, it captures the structure of the graph and the characteristics of both
566 local and latent representations more effectively, as indicated by improved performance
567 measures (Fig. 4). Third, our hyperparameter optimization strategies, combined with analysis of
568 meta-paths, enable biological interpretation of predicted links.

569 While the KG embedding and ML approaches described here have distinct advantages
570 over metapath2vec for link prediction, our model can be further improved through generation of
571 curated training and testing datasets and additional data that capture pathway context. Currently,
572 to generate negative datasets, any missing link between nodes is used as an indication that a
573 relationship does not exist. In short, the negative sample is simply non-connected nodes. In
574 certain knowledge domains turned into KGs this is appropriate, however just because a link does
575 not exist within our graph does not mean it does not occur in a cellular context (i.e., two proteins
576 interacting or a protein having a certain association). To address this limitation, we are currently

577 working on a KG that includes subcellular localization information of proteins, and tissue/cell
578 specificity to create a more informed negative set that better reflects the natural boundaries
579 placed by biology rather than the boundaries of our current knowledge. Additional future
580 directions include fully incorporating edge information into the embeddings used for our model's
581 predictions. Use of edge labels could allow for the use of additional Natural Language
582 Processing (NLP) based models such as Transformers (Bi et al. 2022; Koncel-Kedziorski et al.
583 2019; Xie et al. 2022; Yao et al. 2019).

584 Overall, we have demonstrated that our model can make valid biological predictions even
585 with sparse input through use of node context extracted from the KG. While this current work
586 was focused on placing dark kinases in a pathway context, within the KG are nodes and edge
587 types relevant for PPI and substrate predictions as well (Fig. 1B, Table S1). Therefore, our KG
588 can be further utilized for other predictive tasks and the functionality of the KG can be further
589 expanded by incorporating other forms of data. For example, including information such as cell-
590 type specific expression of kinases could potentially improve the overall model performance
591 while enabling predictions for cell-type specific dark kinase functions and interactions. However,
592 the addition of new data types can significantly alter the topology of the KG. As data is added,
593 new node/edge types and schemas will need to be incorporated into the graph and
594 hyperparameters will again need to be optimized. The protocol described in Results (section 3.2)
595 for testing hyperparameters serves as a framework for continued usage of the KG, and
596 exploration of variability within the random walk process. The code for RegPattern2Vec has
597 been published on GitHub and these methodologies can be applied to additional KGs for other
598 understudied proteins and protein families.

599

600 **Conclusions**

601 We sought to characterize understudied dark kinases utilizing a network-based approach
602 that combines multi-domain knowledge on both well-studied kinases and dark kinases within a
603 single heterogeneous KG. Our method focuses on improvements within the random walk
604 component of the graph embedding process. To accomplish this, we utilized RegPattern2Vec,
605 allowing for the selection of the relevant part(s) of the KG using labeled semantics (regular
606 patterns) to not only learn the local similarity between nodes and edges but also more complex
607 and non-trivial associations which lead to novel *Protein-Pathway* predictions for dark kinases.
608 Our method performs better in terms of scalability for large graphs compared to other network-
609 based methods by sampling the graph more accurately while preserving node/edge context and
610 structure.

611

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621

622 **Competing Interests.**

623 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

624

625 **Author Contributions.**

626 AK, KK, and NK designed the research and model. LH and AK built the Knowledge
627 Graph. AK, MVS, and NG evaluated the model's performance. NG and AK designed and
628 performed comparative analysis of our model to metapath2vec. NG and MVS designed and
629 performed hyperparameter optimization. MVS and NG designed and performed Biological
630 Validation. MVS, NG, KK, and NK analyzed the data and interpreted the results. AK, MVS,
631 KK, NG, and NK wrote the manuscript. MVS, NG, KK, and NK revised the manuscript. All
632 authors read and approved the final manuscript.

633

634 **Data Availability.**

635 The following information was supplied regarding data availability: The analysis code,
636 scripts with instructions and README are available at GitHub:
637 <https://github.com/gravelCompBio/RegPattern2Vec> (DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7541894) The
638 Knowledge Graph itself and the files necessary to generate the embedding are available at (DOI:
639 10.5281/zenodo.7541827)

640

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642

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